

Indika

Developed by: Odd Meter

Article contributed by: Hannes Hamester

Keywords

Abuse, Ethics, Gender Studies, Moral Development, Philosophy, Psychology, Religion, Theology, Trauma

Figure 1. Key art for *Indika* (2024). © Odd Meter. Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

Indika (see Figure 1) is a third-person adventure game that portrays the story of a nun in a surreal version of 19th-century Russia. Developed by the studio Odd Meter and released in 2024, the digital game explores themes such as religion and authority as a young nun named Indika embarks on a dark journey of self-discovery. At the start of the game, players must perform mundane tasks to satisfy Indika's sisters at the convent. However, after she is given the task of delivering a letter, Indika sets off to leave the monastery behind. However, the young woman is not travelling alone, as she is always accompanied by the devil himself, speaking to her in her thoughts. By encountering many strange people on her way, Indika begins to see visions, and her relationship with the devil causes her to question her own

beliefs. As her world falls apart, players must solve puzzles to keep Indika sane, while flashbacks elaborate on her personal background. Overall, the game Indika is known for its immersive storytelling and philosophical perspectives on faith, presenting players with both comedic and tragic confrontations with the church and inner conflict.

Facts

Release date:	May 2, 2024
Developer:	Odd Meter
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Hybrid
Time frame:	4–6 hours
Languages:	German, English, French, Spanish, Russian, Japanese, Polish, Portuguese, Chinese, Ukrainian
Environment:	Access to computers/consoles & controllers
Material:	-
Price:	Around €25

Resonance & Criticism

As a result of Indika's outstanding storytelling, the game was rated very positively across the board, with around 90% positive ratings on Steam and "generally favourable" reviews on Metacritic, as of 2025. Moreover, it has won several awards, for instance the 'Game Designer Award' at the Japan Game Awards 2025, the 'Game Of The Year' as well as 'Best Narrative' awards at the 2025 Games For Change Awards and the 'Best Dialogue For An Indie Game' award at the 23rd Annual Game Audio Network Guild ("INDIKA" on Steam, n.d.). Therefore, most players value Indika for its intense examination of themes such as guilt, faith, identity, and psychological instability. Nevertheless, precisely those themes can be overwhelming for players looking for a simpler experience.

Game Principle & Process

All in all, Indika's gameplay is relatively simple, as players mostly control the character from a third-person perspective and walk through the scenery. Indeed, the dialogue of the game drives the story, and the narrative focuses on the nun's philosophical soul-searching, accompanied by the devil's whispers in her ears. However, as the story progresses and Indika slowly loses her mind, the game utilises unique aesthetics to represent the various plot elements, for instance, puzzle games that reflect on her state of sanity. Furthermore, flashbacks of Indika's past are presented through 2D pixel art to juxtapose her dark present with her joyful, bright background.

Within the game, players can collect points to rank up and increase their level of piety, but the more points a player gets, the more they need. This feedback system is an approach to gamify religion itself, with regard to prayers and deeds earning a believer's way into heaven. Indeed, the developers of Indika clarified that they deliberately designed this feedback system to appear meaningless to test whether players unthinkingly follow instructions or question them (Couture, 2025).

Consequently, the overarching motive of Indika is to criticise the church and faith as an abused instrument of power, used by those in authority to oppress and control the population, especially regarding women. In the case of Indika herself, it is not clear whether she already had mental health problems before she became a nun or whether her involvement in the church caused them. Nevertheless, the criticism of religion shows right at the start of the game, when players need to perform dull tasks to satisfy the other sisters, or when church representatives and the military are seen working together, ultimately using religion as a weapon. By referring to the Russian Orthodox Church, Indika's developers intend to clearly express their disapproval of the system (Gordon, 2024).

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Above all, Indika aims to tell a story about humanity's eternal struggle with itself. That is why, during the game, the question of good and evil is repeatedly raised in contrast to the religious definitions, and players are encouraged to rethink their own understanding of morality. Therefore, the devil, the main character always heard in the back of her mind, is not only meant to represent the biblical creature but rather the dark, forbidden thoughts Indika, or all human beings, carry within. This intentional ambiguity is also found in the other characters of the game, for instance, the devout believer Ilya, an escaped convict whom Indika encounters on her journey. While Ilya prays to God and Indika converses with the devil, they both join forces to seek salvation in a greater power, only to find out that they are responsible for their own fates.

Provided that the developer intends to criticise religion and to display the power faith holds to restrain people, the game Indika deliberately leaves questions unanswered to provoke players to think and seek solutions for themselves (Gordon, 2024). For this reason, Indika can be used to stimulate discussion in ethics or religion courses about the interplay of belief and doubt, the power of institutions, or journeys of self-discovery. Further, the game can be utilized in media education to analyze games as a medium for criticism and reflection. At this time, no information has been published for teachers who wish to implement the game in their curricula.

Effectiveness

To date, no empirical studies have examined the educational value of the game Indika. However, Luan, Chang, and Zeng found in their 2025 article on the educational value of

narrative-driven commercial entertainment games that dialogue-based games, can promote empathy, perspective-taking, and narrative-based reflection. According to the researchers, narrative games are well-suited as a medium for value formation, particularly through immersive stories and symbolic and metaphorical content that foster emotional connections (Luan et al., 2025). As a result, dialogue-based games have substantial educational value when they integrate cultural content in a meaningful way. In fact, video games like *Indika* can strengthen value awareness, promote reflective thinking, build cultural identity, and anchor learning emotionally (Luan et al., 2025). Even though *Indika* was not the focus of the study by Luan et al. (2025), the game nonetheless demonstrates the described qualities and thus has great potential for teaching values and ethics, especially in humanities-oriented learning contexts.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The game *Indika* contains content that is not suitable for all age groups and may trigger some players, such as partial nudity, use of tobacco, violence, consumption of alcohol, cursing, body dismemberment, non-consensual sex, and sexual assault (INDIKA on Steam, n.d.). Especially the depictions of sexual violence in some scenes of the game may cause harm to players. It is advisable to inform players of the presence of these graphic images before play, so that no one is forced to consume potentially disturbing material. Moreover, the intense criticism of religion should also be pointed out to prevent anyone from feeling attacked in their beliefs.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

Couture, J. (2025, March 13). Inside *Indika*'s powerful, bleak exploration of religion. *Game Developer*. <https://www.gamedeveloper.com/design/inside-indika-s-powerful-bleak-exploration-of-religion>

Gordon, L. (2024, May 2). 'Like taking a shovel to your brain': Dark fairytale game *Indika* takes aim at the Russian Orthodox church. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/games/2024/may/02/indika-russian-orthodox-church-fairytale-game-dmitry-svetlov-interview>

Metacritic. (n.d.). *INDIKA* [PC game]. Retrieved October 1, 2025, from <https://www.metacritic.com/game/indika/>

Steam. (n.d.). *INDIKA* [Steam store page]. Retrieved October 1, 2025, from <https://store.steampowered.com/app/1373960/INDIKA/>

Wikipedia contributors. (2025, December 10). Indika (video game). In *Wikipedia*. Retrieved December 10, 2025, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Indika_%28video_game%29

Luan, J., Chang, T., & Zeng, Z. (2025). Research on narrative-driven commercial entertainment games on values education towards China. In *Proceedings of the 2025 2nd International Conference on Informatics Education and Computer Technology Applications (IECA '25)* (pp. 233–239). Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3732801.3732845>